

CONSTRUCTION OF A ROAD BASE FROM SALINE SOILS IN UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION: This article discusses the issues of taking into account the sudden decrease in strength of excess moisture above the standard compaction moisture, as a negative feature of the construction of saline soils in the construction, construction and design of roads under the saline soils in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: automobile roads, pavement, pavement elevation, salinity, saline soils, salts, salt content, lightly soluble salts, etc.

Introduction: Due to the remoteness of the Republic of Uzbekistan from the oceans and seas, one of the major contributors to the development of the country's economy is the highway. Highways are more efficient than air and railways in transporting domestically produced and imported goods from one destination to another, bringing people closer together.

Today, the world pays great attention to the design and construction of various engineering structures, including automobile roads, in areas with saline soils. Scientific and practical research is being carried out in foreign and CIS countries to study the effects of salts on various properties of soils, to improve methods for determining the deformation and mechanical characteristics of saline soils, to substantiate the characteristics of saline soils. As a result, all this allows to develop reliable proposals for the design, construction and operation of roads in saline soils. 46.3% of the total land area of the republic is saline soils of various degrees.

Saline soils are soils that contain more than 0.3% of different amounts and types of soluble salts. Soil salinization is the process of accumulation of water-soluble mineral salts in the soil. Saline soils are mainly distributed in the deserts and semi-deserts of the plains, in some cases in

the desert regions, ie in areas with negative water balance, as well as in areas with unstable component (sulfate, halloid, etc.) hypergenesis [1].

According to the water solubility of salts in saline soils, they are divided into 4 types, listed in Table 1: lightly soluble, moderately soluble, insoluble and very insoluble salts [2].

Types	Solubility level	Solubility value, g/l
1	Lightly soluble	more than 2.0
2	Medium soluble	0,1
3	Hard to dissolve	0,1-0,001
4	Very difficult to dissolve	less than 0.001

Note: 1) The composition of lightly soluble salts includes: chlorides NaCl, KCl, CaCl₂, MgCl₂; bicarbonates: NaNSO₃, Ca (NSO₃)₂, Mg (NSO₃)₂; sodium carbonate Na₂SO₃; magnesium and sodium sulfates MgSO₄, Na₂SO₄; 2) Moderately soluble salts include gypsum CaSO₄ • 2H₂O and anhydrite CaSO₄. In the natural environment of Uzbekistan there are saline soils of different quantities and quality. The most common salts involved in salinization are: NaCl, Na₂SO₄•10H₂O, MgSO₄•7H₂O, MgCL₂•6H₂O, CaCL₂•6H₂O, NaHCO₃, Na₂CO₃•10H₂O, CaCO₃ и CaSO₄•2H₂O [3].

The lightly soluble salts mentioned above have different properties and rapidly change the physical and mechanical properties of soils depending on the quantity and quality of the soil. In order to properly assess the salinity of soils, it is necessary to take into account a complex of basic natural factors that affect salt metabolism, i.e., the amount of precipitation, climatic regime, and so on. Saline soils contain large amounts of gypsum and carbonates in addition to slightly soluble salts [4].

Salts in soils, properties and engineering structures, in particular, are divided into the following groups in terms of their impact on the strength of the footpath [5]:

Group 1 - chloride salts: NaCl, CaCL₂ and MgCL₂. These salts have solubility properties. Soils containing chloride salts have the property of retaining a certain amount of moisture, which

creates good conditions for their compaction even in the dry season of the year. Even when crystallizing in solution, the volume of the chloride salts itself does not increase.

Group 2 - sulfate and magnesium salts: Na_2SO_4 and MgSO_4 . These salts have the property of combining a certain amount of water molecules. Sodium sulfate combines 10 molecules of water. At a temperature of 32.40 C, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is converted to an anhydrous form. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, when the air temperature varies from 50 to 400, it creates good conditions for the periodic coagulation and the presence of crystalline waters of crystal hydrates. The latter breaks the bond between the soil particles, resulting in the formation of "fluff".

Group 3 -sodium carbonate salts: NaHCO_3 and Na_2CO_3 . These salts are relatively rare in the soil. An aqueous solution of soda has an alkaline reaction that allows maximum dispersion of clay-colloid fractions in soils.

Group 4 - sulfate and sodium carbonate salts. They are abundant in the soil - from 2% to 60% and more. According to the road classification, salinities include soils with chloride, sulfur and carbonic salts of lightly soluble sodium, calcium and magnesium in the upper one-meter layer by more than 0.3% by mass [6]. Since lightly soluble salts have different and complex effects on the soil, the allowable criterion for the amount of salt in the soil, as well as the numerical limit of salinity is obtained as a summary of indicators that determine the characteristics and level of salinity in the soil property. Such an indicator is the characteristic moisture of the soil, its resistance to loading (shear, compression, compression) at constant absolute and relative humidity, maximum density at standard compaction, water resistance, as well as the ability to leach in the soil when wet with water-insoluble salts, water and atmospheric precipitation. . If the amount of salt later exceeds the accepted criterion, it is better not to use the given soil in the construction of the footpath, as its strength and water resistance will quickly decrease.

In the process of designing and constructing the pavement of highways, it should be taken into account that the negative properties in the construction of saline soils are a sudden decrease in strength in excess of favorable humidity at standard compaction. Such soils may lose their bond

when dry and their density decreases as a result of the formation of crystal hydrates. Therefore, measures are taken to ensure high strength of the pavement, especially at the top of the lift (at a depth of not less than 50 cm below the pavement), which limits the seasonal fluctuations of soil moisture and density.

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